

Product Wavefunction and the Nikiforov-Uvarov Method for the Schrodinger Equation

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Aug. 29, 2019

In a series of notes (1), we suggested one may compare the Schrodinger equation, with the ground state solution removed, to a general hypergeometric equation:

$p(x) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W_1(x) + q(x) \frac{d}{dx} W_1(x) + C_1 W_1(x) = 0$ ((1)) where $p(x)$ is at most quadratic in x and $q(x)$ is at most linear. Such an equation has known Rodrigues polynomial solutions (2). To remove the ground state, we write $W(x) = W_0(x)W_1(x)$ where $W(x)$ is the full wavefunction of a bound state and $W_0(x)$, the ground state (or another state). Inserting into the time-independent Schrodinger equation leads to the coupled equation:

$$-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W_1(x) - 1/m \frac{d}{dx} W_1(x) \left[\frac{d}{dx} W_0(x) / W_0(x) \right] = (E - E_0) W_1(x) \quad ((2))$$

Recently in 2006, a more general method was presented in the literature (3). In this method, $W(x) = f(x)F(x)$, $E = E_f + E_F$ and $V = V_f + V_F$. These values are inserted into the time-independent Schrodinger equation and compared with the Nikiforov-Uvarov method equation. This general method was applied to a specific case of Jacobi polynomials and V_F found to be 0.

In the case that $V_F = 0$, $f(x)$ is a solution of the time-independent Schrodinger equation and this general method is the same as the one presented in (1). In fact, it seems in the example in (3), V_F is forced to equal 0 which may imply the more general method is very similar to the method of (1). The objective of this note is to compare the two methods.

Method of (3)

In (3), the Nikiforov-Uvarov (NU) approach and not the general hypergeometric DE ((1)) is the starting point. The NU approach yields solutions for a DE of the form:

$$\frac{d}{dy} \frac{d}{dy} F(y=s(x)) + t_1(s)/s_1(s) \frac{d}{dy} F + s_2/(s_1*s_1) F = 0 \quad ((3))$$

s_1 and s_2 are at most quadratic polynomials in $y=s(x)$ and t_1 is linear.

The authors of (3) use $W(x) = f(x)F(s(x))$, where $y=s(x)$ is a transformation, which they insert into the time-independent Schrodinger equation obtaining:

$$\frac{d}{dy} \frac{d}{dy} F(s) + \left\{ \frac{(d/dx \ d/dx \ s) / (d/dx \ s)^2 + 2 \ d/d \ f / [(d/dx \ s) \ f]}{[f \ (d/dx \ s)^2 + (E-V)/[(d/dx \ s)^2]} \right\} \frac{d}{dy} F(s) + \left\{ \frac{(d/dx \ d/dx \ f)}{[f \ (d/dx \ s)^2 + (E-V)/[(d/dx \ s)^2]} \right\} F(s) = 0 \quad ((4))$$

They then identify:

$(d/dx \ d/dx \ f) / f = V_f - E_f$ (a Schrodinger equation result containing V_f i.e. part of the potential)

$$VF - EF = -s^1 / (s^2 * s^2) (d/dx s)^2$$

$$\text{and } f(x) = (d/dx s)^{-1/2} \exp \left[\frac{1}{2} \int (\text{upper bound } s(x) \quad t^1/s^1 ds) \right]$$

Thus, it seems the authors of (3) are not looking upon $f(x)$ as a solution of the Schrodinger equation, although it becomes one if $VF=0$.

This general approach is then applied to a Jacobi polynomial problem where:

$$VF - EF = C_2 (d/dx s)^2 / [1 - s^*s]$$

(See details in (3).)

The authors of (3) argue: "Since we have a constant (EF) on the left-hand side, there must be at least one term on the right-hand side, from which a constant arises." (3)

They then set: $C_1 = C_2 (d/dx s)^2 / [1 - s^*s]$ ((5)) or $VF=0$. In the approach of (1), $VF=0$ right at the beginning. It seems that $VF=0$ is being forced to zero. If that is the case, the general method of (3) seems to collapse to the method of (1).

If VF is forced to 0, then $f(x)$ is a solution of the Schrodinger equation and the coefficient of $F(x)$ in ((4)) becomes:

$$\left\{ \frac{d/dx d/dx f}{f} / \left[\frac{d/dx s}{s} \right]^2 + (E - V) / \left[\frac{d/dx s}{s} \right]^2 \right\} = (E - E_0)$$

because $f(x)$ is a solution of the Schrodinger equation with energy E_0 . Thus, the coefficient of $F(x)$ is a constant forcing the coefficient of $d/dy F$ in ((4)) to be of the form: $c s(x) + b$ where c and b are unknown constants. Thus, ((4)) is compared to the general hypergeometric DE ((1)).

The authors of (3) choose $s(x) = \cos(ax)$ where $C = a^*a$ as a solution of ((5)) but point out there are other solutions. They then obtain a potential:

$$V_f = C_3 \csc^2(ax) + C_4 \csc(a) \cot(a) \quad ((6)) \text{ where } C_3 \text{ and } C_4 \text{ are constants.}$$

Method of (1)

We compare the method of (3) with that of (1). In (1), $VF=0$ automatically and $f(x) = W_0(x)$. The Schrodinger equation with $W(x) = W_0(x)W_1(s(x))$ where $s(x) = y$ is a transformation leads to the equation:

$$-1/2m [d/dx s]^2 d/dy d/dy W1 + (\{ (d/dx d/dx s) + 2 (d/dx s) d/dx f / [f] \}) - (E-Eo) W1 = 0 \quad ((7))$$

In order for ((7)) to be of hypergeometric form ((1)):

$$\{ (d/dx d/dx s) + 2 (d/dx s) d/dx f / [f] \} = cy + b \quad ((8))$$

and $(d/dx s)^2$ must be a quadratic or lower in s . If $s(x) = \cos(ax)$ as in (3), then

$$(d/dx s)^2 = a^2 \sin(ax) \sin(ax) = a^2 (1 - s^2) \quad ((8))$$

Thus, the quadratic condition is met. The goal becomes to solve ((8)) where:

$$d/dx d/dx s(x) = -a^2 \cos(ax) = -a^2 y \quad \text{and} \quad d/dx s = -a \sin(ax) = -a \sqrt{1-y^2}$$

Note:

$$d/dx (d/d f / f) + (d/dx f / f)^2 = d/d d/dx f / f \quad \text{and} \quad ((9))$$

$$d/d d/dx f = -2m(Eo-V) f \quad ((10))$$

Let $g(x) = d/dx f / f$ then:

$$-a^2 y - 2 a \sqrt{1-y^2} \sqrt{ -2m(Eo-V) - d/dx g } = c y + b \quad ((11))$$

$$4a^2 (1-y^2) \{ -2m(Eo-V) - d/dx g \} = [a^2 y + (cy+b)]^2 \quad ((12))$$

One may obtain g from ((8)) and hence $d/dx g$ i.e.

$$g = (C1 \cos(ax) + C2) / \sin(ax) \quad \text{and} \quad d/dx g = C3 \cot^2(ax) + C4 \csc^2(ax) + C5$$

Equation ((11)) then yields:

$$V(x) = \text{constant} + C6 \cot^2(ax) + C7 \csc^2(ax) + C8 \cos(ax) / [\sin^2(ax)] \quad ((12))$$

Noting : $1 + \cot^2(ax) = \csc^2(ax)$ one has a potential of the same form as in (3).

Conclusion

In conclusion, it seems the method of (1) is identical to that of (3) if $VF=0$. If one forces VF to be zero, it seems this is the equivalent to model (1) with $VF=0$ as an initial condition. The results of the two methods yield the same result for the example considered in (3).

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Quantum Excited States and the Hypergeometric Differential Equation, Hypergeometric Differential Equation for Klein Gordon Excited State (preprint, zenodo, 2019)
2. Robin, W. On the Rodrigues Formula Solution of the Hypergeometric-Type Differential Equation (2013)
<http://www.m-hikari.com/imf/imf-2013/29-32-2013/robinIMF29-32-2013.pdf>
3. Gonul, B and Koksai, K. A Search on the Nikiforov-Uvarov Method (2006)
<http://cds.cern.ch/record/940783/files/0604021.pdf>